

Climate Resilient Odisha Produce Study (CROPS)

Statistical Analysis Plan

Outcomes: Dietary Diversity, Mid-Upper Arm Circumference, Water Security, Food Security

Version 1.0, March 2026

Trial Registration: ISRCTN79401136

Protocol Version: Main Study Protocol v4.0

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background and Rationale

Malnutrition, including micronutrient deficiency and macronutrient deficiency, remains a major public health problem. Malnutrition in-utero and during childhood can have lifelong consequences, including associations with lower adult height, educational attainment, income, and offspring birthweight¹. Despite the country's economic growth, malnutrition rates have remained high in India,² where it remains the primary risk factor for mortality and morbidity in children under five³.

The Climate Resilient Odisha Produce Study (CROPS) is a randomized controlled trial (RCT) evaluating the impact of a climate-resilient agriculture intervention on dietary diversity in rural India. CROPS' Principal Investigators and Emory researchers, Dr. Sheela Sinharoy and Dr. Thomas Clasen, have a longstanding research partnership with Gram Vikas, a non-profit organization based in Odisha, India. Their previous study of a water, sanitation, and hygiene (WASH) intervention in Odisha found that 33.3% of children under five years old living in intervention villages were stunted⁴. Notably, despite the provision of piped water supplies, the intervention did not significantly impact household crop production or dietary diversity; only 30.6% of children aged six to 23 months had adequate dietary diversity in the day prior to survey at endline⁵.

Homestead gardening has improved dietary diversity in before-and-after RCTs, but little is known about whether such approaches can maintain dietary diversity across seasons. Other studies have found that the effects of programs on nutritional outcomes seemingly wane over time, possibly due to a lack of irrigation and fencing⁶. In Odisha, rainfall is increasingly erratic in the post-monsoon period,⁷ making provisions for irrigation crucial.

1.2 CROPS Overview

The CROPS intervention was co-designed and developed by Gram Vikas, Emory, and community members over the course of 18 months of formative research and piloting. CROPS includes community meetings/trainings aimed to: (a) build knowledge, skills, and self-efficacy related to climate-smart agricultural techniques for year-round production of fruits and vegetables through backyard gardens; (b) improve knowledge of the importance of dietary

diversity for all household members and self-efficacy related to food preparation and distribution; (c) increase women's negotiating and decision-making power in the household.

Hardware distributed to households included seeds and seedlings, supplies for integrated pest management (e.g., fencing material, sticky traps), and greywater capture and re-use supplies to enable irrigation in seasons of water scarcity (e.g., PVC pipes, drums). Gram Vikas had principal responsibility for delivering the intervention. Emory field teams supported GV's delivery of the intervention, including the acquisition and delivery of hardware components. Emory was not able to separate team members who participated in these implementation activities from those engaged in data collection.

1.3 Study Objectives

The primary objective of CROPS is to evaluate the impact of a climate-smart agriculture intervention on dietary diversity among people living in rural districts of Odisha, India. Details of the CROPS study are set forth in a protocol dated March 12, 2024 (ver. 1.0) and amended as of August 12, 2025 (ver. 4.0). This document details the statistical analysis plan (SAP) for the primary outcome as well as secondary outcomes of mid-upper arm circumference, water security, and food security.

2. STUDY METHODS

2.1 Trial Design

CROPS is an open (non-blinded), parallel, two-arm cluster randomized trial with community-level randomization (i.e., 41 intervention and 41 control communities). The communities included in the initial sampling frame were identified by Gram Vikas and included current or former program areas, also known as the Water Secure Gram Panchayat (WSGP) program (e.g., WSGP or MANTRA^a). Emory subsequently narrowed the sampling frame to communities that had a functional water source at the time of enrollment. Households that met the inclusion/exclusion criteria within these communities and who consented to participate were enrolled in the study (Section 4.1). Participants were followed longitudinally, on a rolling basis, in four separate survey rounds between May 2024 and March 2026. The trial was reviewed by the Institutional Review Board of Emory University (STUDY00007613 date 12 April 2024) and in India by the Independent Ethics Committee of XIM University (XU2024520212VC dated 24 May 2024). The RCT is registered as "Promoting homestead gardens to improve dietary diversity in Rural India: a randomized controlled trial", ISRCTN79401136, <https://doi.org/10.1186/ISRCTN79401136> (dated May 2024).

^a MANTRA included construction of a water tower and reticulated distribution system to each household, piped water connections in the toilet, bathing room, and either kitchen or backyard 'washing up' area, and where 100% of households had built connected toilet and bathing rooms

2.2 Randomization

Three adjacent districts in Odisha were selected (Ganjam, Gajapati and Nayagarh) to ensure diversity among the sample while also maintaining feasibility for the implementation team. Participating communities in Ganjam are located closer to the market and coast, those in Gajapati are situated in hilly terrains, and those in Nayagarh are situated on plains. Within each district, communities were selected from among a list provided by Gram Vikas. This resulted in a total of 82 communities (i.e., section of a village, a village, or two villages combined) that each had at least 25 households. Communities were cluster randomized to either the intervention or control arm.

Within each community, all households were approached to determine eligibility (Section 4.1). Inclusion criteria were organized into two tiers. Tier 1: Households with at least one child under five years old at the time of the survey OR at least one pregnant woman living in the household at the time of the survey. Tier 2: Households with suitable space for a backyard garden (ideally backyard space that is no less than 100 square feet, has good soil, receives ample sunlight, and is situated near and/or below the outlet of the toilet and bathing room) OR an intact and functional bathroom room OR strong interest and motivation to participate in CROPS and who are willing and available to attend community meetings and household visits.

If at least 25 households were eligible according to Tier 1 criteria and consented to participate in the study, recruitment in the community stopped here. If fewer than 25 households were eligible according to Tier 1 criteria, the study team returned to the community to recruit and enroll the remaining number of households according to Tier 2 criteria.

Following enrollment, consent, and baseline, the participating 82 villages were randomly assigned to intervention and control arms on a 1:1 basis. Baseline data from Tier 1 eligible households was then reviewed to check that the intervention and control groups were generally balanced on a number of key variables. These included the baseline level of the primary outcome of women's dietary diversity and variables hypothesized to be predictors or confounders of change in dietary diversity (i.e., caste, wealth, household food insecurity, household water insecurity, available backyard space for a garden, total number of households in the community). Communities were re-randomized once as the initial randomization was not balanced for household food security.

2.3 Masking

Masking of the study population was not feasible because of the nature of the intervention. Prior to formal analysis, a research staff member will scramble the villages with a fake variable for intervention arm. Once all analysis code is written and tested with the dummy intervention arm variable, the analyst will be provided the true study arm assignment variable.

2.4 Trial Framework

CROPS is a superiority trial. The primary intention-to-treat (ITT) analysis is a test of statistical significance to evaluate whether outcome data are consistent with the hypothesis that there is no difference between the intervention and control arms. If there is evidence of substantial heterogeneity in fidelity and/or adherence, per-protocol (PP) analyses will also be conducted.

2.5 Statistical Interim Analyses

Interim analyses may be required for donor reporting.

2.6 Timing of Analysis

All official analyses will be conducted once data collection is complete and the SAP has been approved and registered.

2.7 Timing of Outcome and Covariate Assessments

Following the initial baseline survey (May-December 2024), data will be collected at three follow-up (FU) rounds over the course of one full year: FU-1 (April-August 2025), FU-2 (September-December 2025), and FU-3 (December 2025-March 2026); dates are approximate.

Time-invariant covariates (e.g., caste, household size) will only be collected once, primarily at baseline. Other covariates (e.g., decision making power, whether a household member farms off-site) will be collected at multiple time points during the study.

Outliers will be monitored throughout data collection for all covariates and outcomes. If values exceed what was determined to be infeasible or highly unlikely prior to data collection, the enumeration team will be asked to verify their response (i.e., identify it as a typo or revisit the household).

3. STATISTICAL PRINCIPLES

3.1 Confidence Intervals and P-Values

We will use 95% confidence intervals for the purposes of estimation of outcomes. Analysis of all outcomes and effect modification will use $\alpha=0.05$ to evaluate statistical significance. A Benjamini-Hochberg procedure will be used to adjust for multiple comparisons in subgroup analyses with more than two categories (false discovery rate = 0.2) .

3.2 Protocol Deviations

PP analyses will include all controls but restrict to intervention households that received the intervention with fidelity and were adherent.

Fidelity will be assessed with indicators such as:

- 1) Receiving seeds (self-reported)
- 2) Receiving any greywater materials (e.g., piping, drum, ladle, cement works) (self-reported)
- 3) Receiving fencing (self-reported)
- 4) Receiving sticky traps (self-reported)
- 5) Receiving spray head for pesticides (self-reported)
- 6) CROPS staff visited at least once (self-reported)

Adherence will be assessed with indicators such as:

- 1) Attending community meetings (self-reported)
- 2) Having fencing erected (observed)
- 3) Having sticky traps (observed)
- 4) Having a functional greywater system (observed)

3.3 Analysis Populations

The ITT will include all participants with at least one outcome measurement (i.e., not lost to follow-up at every time point). PP analyses will include complete cases for each timepoint, or those not missing a priori covariates and confounders.

4. TRIAL POPULATION

4.1 Eligibility

Community inclusion/exclusion criteria

- Communities were included if they were currently/formerly part of Gram Vikas' MANTRA/WSGP programs and had a functional piped water supply (as reported by Gram Vikas or visited by the Emory team)
- Communities were excluded if they did not have year-round access to a road

Household inclusion/exclusion criteria

Inclusion criteria were organized into two tiers:

- Tier 1: Households with at least one child under five years old at the time of the survey OR at least one pregnant woman living in the household at the time of the survey

- Tier 2: Households with suitable space for a backyard garden (ideally backyard space that is no less than 100 square feet, has good soil, receives ample sunlight, and is situated near and/or below the outlet of the toilet and bathing room) OR an intact and functional bathroom room OR strong interest and motivation to participate in CROPS and who are willing and available to attend community meetings and household visits.

4.2 Recruitment

If at least 25 households were eligible according to Tier 1 criteria and consented to participate in the study, recruitment in the community stopped here. If fewer than 25 households were eligible according to Tier 1 criteria, the team returned to the community to recruit and enroll more households according to Tier 2 criteria.

4.3 Withdrawal/Follow-up

We define loss to follow-up as any reason that contributes to a missing outcome value. Reasons for dropping out of the study, such as migration, death, or withdrawal will be recorded.

4.4 Participant Characteristics

For ITT and PP analyses, the participant characteristics listed in Table 1 will be reported. Counts/percentages will be calculated for categorical variables. If continuous variables are approximately normally distributed, mean and standard deviation will be reported. Otherwise, median and interquartile range will be reported. The count and percent of missing, refused, and “Don’t know” data will also be reported for each variable. In ITT, the variables will be disaggregated by intervention and control households.

Table 1. Baseline characteristics to be reported

Variable	Type	Definition/assessment method
Household characteristics		
Household size	Continuous	Number of people living in the house including respondent
Wealth index	Continuous	Asset-based principal component analysis
Food security	Binary (less than two) and Continuous/Ordinal (0-8)	Food Insecurity Experiences Scale (FIES) ⁸
Water security	Binary (less than 4) and Continuous/Ordinal (0-12)	Shortened Household Water Insecurity Experiences (HWISE-4) scale ⁹
Available space for a garden	Continuous	Enumerator estimate of total backyard space available for gardening
Respondent characteristics		
Caste	Categorical	Categories: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scheduled tribe • Scheduled caste • Other backward caste • General • Other
Age	Continuous	Respondent asked age
Education	Categorical	Categories: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Never attended school • Anganwadi • Grades 1 - 5 • Grades 6 - 10 • Some secondary school • Completed secondary school • Degree incomplete • Degree complete • Higher
Religion	Categorical	Categories: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hindu • Christian • Muslim • Other
Minimum Dietary Diversity (MDD)	Binary (at least five) and Continuous/Ordinal (0-10)	Number of food groups consumed in day prior ¹⁰
Child <5 characteristics		
Gender	Binary	Reported by caretaker
Age	Continuous	Calculated based on reported birthdate
MDD	6-23 months: Binary (at least five) Continuous/Ordinal (0-8) 24-59 months: Binary (at least four) Continuous/Ordinal (0-7)	Number of food groups consumed in day prior ¹¹

5. DATA ANALYSES

5.1 Outcome Definitions

Table 2 provides the outcome definitions for the outcomes discussed in this SAP.

Table 2. Definitions of CROPS outcomes to be analyzed

Outcome	Type	Maximum number of timepoints measured per household (excluding baseline)	Definition	Note
Women's MDD ¹⁰	Binary	3	Consuming at least five of 10 food groups in day prior to survey	Not specifically validated for women over age 49, but shown to be reliable proxy for micronutrient adequacy in other contexts ¹²
MDD for children ages 6-59 months ¹¹	Binary	3 per child	<u>Children 6-23 months:</u> Consuming at least 5 of 8 food groups in day prior to survey <u>Children 24-59 months:</u> Consuming at least 4 of 7 food groups in day prior to survey (removes breastmilk)	Not validated for children 24-59 months, but shown to be a reliable proxy for micronutrient adequacy in other contexts ^{13,14}
Men's MDD	Binary	3	Consuming at least five of 10 food groups in day prior to survey	Not specifically validated for men, but shown to be reliable proxy for micronutrient adequacy in other contexts ¹²
Non-wasting of women ¹⁵	Binary	2	MUAC \geq 23 cm	The appropriate cut-off for women's wasting is debated
Non-wasting of children ages 6-59 months ¹⁶	Binary	2 per child	MUAC \geq 11.5 cm	N/A
Household water security ⁹	Binary	3	HWISE-4 < 4	N/A
Household food security ⁸	Binary	3	FIES < 4	N/A

5.2 Intention-to-Treat Analysis

5.2.1 Minimum dietary diversity in adult women

The primary outcome analyzed will be MDD in women. Although this measure for dietary diversity has only been specifically validated and endorsed for women aged 15 to 49, we will apply this measure to all women in the sample based on evidence from other contexts that it also predicts micronutrient adequacy for older women.¹² We will regress binary dietary diversity, reported in all available FU surveys (i.e., maximum three repeated measures per woman), on trial arm and time using generalized estimating equations (GEE) with an exchangeable working correlation and robust standard errors at the community level.

From prior data, we know the outcome is unlikely to be rare (i.e., more than 10% of women will achieve dietary diversity), so we will first attempt log-binomial models to estimate the risk ratio. If the log binomial models do not converge, we will use Poisson regression with robust standard errors as an approximation. Our model will include a penalized spline term for continuous time^b:

$$\log(P[Y_{ijt} = 1]) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{arm}_i + f(\text{time}_{ijt}) \text{ where } Y_{ijt} = 1 \text{ if woman } j \text{ in community } i \text{ achieves MDD at observation } t$$

There will be no imputation of missing data. Significance will be assessed with two-sided Wald p-values ($\alpha=0.05$).

Sensitivity/supplemental analyses

- To assess potential differential courtesy bias, we will use GEE logistic regression to compare the odds of intervention and control households ($\alpha=0.05$) reporting our negative control (namely, consumption of foods identified as rare/inaccessible in Odisha)
- We will conduct a sensitivity analysis where we exclude participants who reported that 1) they ate more or less food because of a religious holiday or 2) they abstained from or ate certain foods because of a religious observation the day before the survey
- If there is evidence of differential loss-to-follow up (>10%) between the intervention and controls, we will use inverse probability of censorship to also conduct weighted regressions
- If there are meaningful baseline imbalances between the intervention and controls, we will account for this using g-computation (marginal standardization) with village-level bootstrapped confidence intervals
- We will explore the potential of intervention effect modification by time (due to intervention roll-out or seasonality) using an interaction between arm and time
- Since the full intervention delivery was completed only by FU 3 (January-March 2026), we will also develop models that only include that outcome measure

^b There were 3 repeated measures per women, and data were collected nearly continuously throughout the year

- We will also analyze the dietary diversity outcome as an ordinal variable (with categories for number of food groups consumed) using a GEE proportional odds model (i.e., logistic GEE) OR as a count using a GEE Poisson or GEE negative binomial (if there is evidence of overdispersion)
- We will also model each food group separately to determine whether the intervention impacted some groups more than others

5.2.2 Secondary outcomes

5.2.2.1 Minimum dietary diversity in children and adult men

To determine if effects of the intervention were equitable among household members, we will also separately analyze the effect of the intervention on men, children 6-23 months, and children 24-59 months old:

- For men, we will use the same definition of dietary diversity used for women (although the measure has not been validated for men) and the same analytic method
- For children, we will define achieving minimum dietary diversity as consuming at least 5/8 or 4/7 food groups based on age (Table 2)

We will use a similar analytic approach as described in section 5.2.1. We will use GEE (log link) with robust standard errors accounting for clustering at the community level; RRs will be reported.

5.2.2.2 Mid-upper arm circumference in women and children

Models will be developed separately for women and children ages 6-59 months. The MUAC non-wasting cut-offs we will use for women and children will be ≥ 23 cm and ≥ 11.5 cm, respectively (Table 2). We will regress binary wasting status reported in all available follow-up surveys (i.e., maximum two repeated measures per individual) on trial arm and a penalized spline for continuous time (based on the date of data collection) using GEE (log link) with an exchangeable working correlation and robust standard errors at the community level:

$$\log(P[Y_{ijt} = 1]) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{arm}_i + f(\text{time}_{ijt}) \text{ where } Y_{ijt} = 1 \text{ if individual } j \text{ in community } i \text{ is not wasted at observation } t$$

We will also explore the MUAC outcome as a continuous variable using a linear GEE.

5.2.2.3 Water security and food security

Models will be developed separately for household water security and household food security. We will regress binary household resource security (i.e., water or food) reported in all available follow-up surveys (i.e., maximum three repeated measures per individual) on trial arm and a

penalized spline for continuous time (based on the date of data collection) using GEE with an exchangeable working correlation and robust standard errors at the community level:

$$\log(P[Y_{ijt} = 1]) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{arm}_i + f(\text{time}_{ijt}) \text{ where } Y_{ijt} = 1 \text{ if household } j \text{ in community } i \text{ is resource secure at observation } t$$

We will explore models that include an interaction term for baseline water security to predict food security:

$$\log(P[Y_{ijt} = 1]) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{arm}_i + \beta_2 \text{baseline water security}_{ij} + \beta_3 \text{arm}_i \times \text{water security}_{ij} + f(\text{time}_{ijt}) \text{ where } Y_{ijt} = 1 \text{ if household } j \text{ in community } i \text{ is food secure at observation } t$$

5.3 Per-Protocol Analyses

Individual-level PP analyses will only be conducted if there is evidence of heterogeneity in fidelity and/or adherence. These analyses will include all controls but restrict to intervention households that received the intervention with fidelity and were adherent (section 3.2). A priori confounders will be identified using Directed Acyclic Graphs (DAGs) for each outcome.

A collinearity assessment will be conducted to determine if any confounding variables need to be rescaled or removed from PP models. If there are issues with convergence, we will use Quasi-Information Criterion (QIC) to determine the model with the best fit after removing predictors.

Statistical interaction will be explored for exposure and the following variables:

- Women covariates: (1) district (2) wealth quintiles (3) age (4) education (5) food insecurity (6) living with mother-in-law
- Child covariates: (1) gender (2) age (3) participation in Anganwadi
- Household/cluster covariates: (1) district (2) wealth quintiles (3) caste (4) religion (5) household size

Subgroup analyses may additionally be used to improve interpretability for categorical effect modifiers with more than two groups.

5.4 Analysis Replication Plan

There are no plans to replicate the analysis. However, Quarto will be used to develop code and generate figures for the results section, which will easily facilitate replication, as desired.

5.5. Data Availability

The datasets will be available upon request from Sheela Sinharoy (sheela.sinharoy@emory.edu).

6. REFERENCES

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